

THE METHODOLOGY OF INTRODUCING INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS TO THE MANAGEMENT OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence, the ways of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence based on international standards, the tasks of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are studied. Also, current issues of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are analyzed.

Key words: institutional independence, principle, mechanism, improvement, theoretical-methodological basis, international standards, management, managerial competencies, academic, educational determinants, marketing, management, integration, forecasting, globalization, functional, digitized system.

INTRODUCTION.

Knowledge is the decisive factor of sustainable socio-economic development and competitiveness of modern society. The economy of knowledge makes special demands on the higher education system to ensure the increase of developed intellectual capital. The successful development of the higher education system is largely determined by the appropriateness of management principles, methods and approaches used in modern conditions.

In the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" "On the systematic development of higher education institutions and improvement of management activities , as an experiment, it is envisaged to expropriate and privatize some state higher educational institutions (except for higher military educational institutions), while retaining at least 51 percent of the state's share, and introduce the principles of corporate governance in them.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Among the scientists of our country, U.S.H. N.K. Yoldoshev, I.U. Majidov, D.Kh. Nabiyev, R.I. Nurimbetov, B.Kh. Rakhimov, D.N. Rakhimova, R.A. Rakhmanbayeva, M.Kh. Saidov, A.N. Samadov, T.S.H. Shodiyev, Sh.D. Ergashkhodjayeva, A.T. Yusupov, Sh. Kurbanov and others.

N.V. Demidov, S.V. Sulima, S.A. scientists from CIS countries. Druzhilov, K.I. Morozova, S.D.Reznik, S.M.Vasin, O.A.Sazikina, O.Bichkova, L.Verbitskaya, V.Kasevich, M.V.Niyazova, V.YE.Varavenko, Johan G. Vissema, F.Altbach, P.Y.Grishina, R.N.Abramov, E.V. Galajinsky, In the scientific works of A.O.Grudzinsky, R.Dim, V.Konnov, M.Repina and others, methodological aspects of the introduction of the principles of institutional independence were studied and analyzed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The introduction of our country into the system of market relations, which caused many social, organizational, economic, institutional, cultural, personnel, ethical and other problems, had an impact on the field of higher education. Reform of the sector, oriented towards the innovative direction of development, requires the development of mixed models using market mechanisms to increase the efficiency of the sphere of social importance and the flexible policy of state regulation.

The process of adapting the management to the market principles in macro-level higher education, where the tendency of the growth of mass demand for higher education is clearly visible, mainly occurs as a result of administrative reforms, the introduction of new state management and the reduction of the state's share in financing higher education. . The market approach emphasizes the importance of system competitiveness, efficiency, accountability, transparency and quality in evaluating the effectiveness of higher education. At the micro level, these trends force higher education institutions (hereinafter HEIs) to actively diversify their sources of income and financial flows, introduce modern management and budgeting methods, and focus their activities on the client. In accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 967 of December 3, 2019 "On the gradual transfer of higher education institutions to the self-financing system", "Independence of HEIs, institutional independence, the role of state intervention is decreasing, creating a basis for independent management of resources, development and implementation of strategic decisions. Institutional changes in higher education are aimed at expanding the level of freedom of universities, because market mechanisms are often more effective than administrative mechanisms in regulating the supply and demand for different forms of education offered to different groups of customers.

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CONCLUSION. In order to implement such projects, it is enough for each individual region to conduct a deep analysis and search for a solution. There is no single recipe or magic formula for the world-class universities that many of us aspire to. It's just that each country should be able to choose the right strategy from various development methods that matches its potential and resources. Uzbekistan is also following the most correct and effective path it has chosen in this regard.

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